

Deep water

Character association and path coefficient analysis of deepwater rices

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Correlation and path coefficient analysis are important tools in determining the contribution of cultivar characters to yield and its components. Correlation coefficient reveals the association between two characters. Path analysis partitions correlation coefficients into direct and indirect effects and indicates the relative significance to yield for each component character.

Fifteen floating rices — local selections GT53, GT60, GT61, GT64, GT76, GT92, GT93, GT103, GT105, DW48, DW6172A, DW6255, GMS12, GMS13, and standard variety Jalmagna — were sown April 1979, before the onset of monsoons. Plots were 5 × 2 m in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Uncontrolled flooding started on 27 June, reached 280 cm 21 August, remained constant for about a week, and then gradually declined at 1-2

Table 2. Path coefficient analysis of deepwater rice characters

Character	Plant height	Panicle bearing tillers	Aquatic tillers/plant	Days to flowering	Days to maturity	Correlation with yield
Plant height	0.76 ^a	0.16	0.06	0.23	-0.30	0.91
Panicle bearing tillers	-0.33	-0.36 ^a	0.02	-0.30	0.48	-0.49
Aquatic tillers/plant	-0.12	0.02	-0.35 ^a	0.51	-0.52	-0.34
Days to flowering	-0.07	-0.04	0.08	-2.33 ^a	2.50	0.14
Days to maturity	-0.09	-0.07	-0.07	-2.33	2.50 ^a	0.06
Residual			0.38			

^aDirect effect.

cm/ day.

The number of days to 50% flowering varied from 172 to 180; that to maturity was 196 to 215 days. Plant length varied from 290 cm for GT105 to 390 cm for Jalmagna.

Characters among the varieties studied differed significantly. Genotypic correlations were generally higher than phenotypic correlations. Only plant height showed a significant positive correlation with yield at both genotypic and phenotypic levels (Table 1). Other characters were not significantly associated with yield or with each other, except days to flowering and days to maturity.

Path analysis showed direct positive effects of plant height and days to maturity on yield (Table 2). Other

attributes had negative direct effects. But days to flowering showed maximum indirect effects, followed by panicle bearing tillers/ plant through days to flowering and number of aquatic tillers/ plant through days to flowering.

Plant height and days to maturity were the principal characters responsible for yield in these deepwater rices, but the positive residual indicates that other characters might also contribute.

Screening for ufra resistance in deepwater rice

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Ufra disease of rice, caused by the nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*, causes serious deepwater rice crop losses in Bangladesh and several South Asian countries. Control methods exist but are not widely accepted. The following method of screening rice varieties for ufra was evolved in an experimental deepwater tank but could be adapted for field testing.

Layout and seedling establishment

1. Divide the tank into 1-m³ plots and make a 15- to 20-cm-high plastered mud levee around each plot. There should be 1 m between plots.
2. Sow rice seeds in line, with 15 cm between lines. Use one row for each variety. After germination thin to 20 seedlings/line.

Table 1. Correlation coefficients between 6 characters of deepwater rice, Uttar Pradesh, India.^a

Character ^b	Plant height	Panicle bearing tillers/plant	Aquatic tillers/plant	Days to flowering	Days to maturity
Yield/plot					
G	0.91**	-0.49	-0.34	0.14	0.04
Ph	0.51*	-0.27	-0.14	0.12	0.01
Plant height					
G		-0.44	-0.16	-0.10	-0.12
Ph		-0.30	-0.13	-0.10	-0.10
Panicle bearing tillers/plant					
G			-0.05	0.13	0.19
Ph			-0.08	0.07	0.12
Aquatic tillers/plant					
G				-0.22	-0.21
Ph				-0.17	-0.19
Days to flowering					
G					1.00**
Ph					0.94**

^a**P = 0.01, *P = 0.05. ^bG =genotypic, Ph = phenotypic.

Inoculation method

1. Take several ufra-infested plants and tease them longitudinally. Cut into small pieces and soak in water overnight. Examine the extraction under a microscope and estimate *D. angustus* population per plant. Prepare an inoculum to ensure each seedling in the test receives 100 nematodes. Infested plants should be teased as before, cut into small pieces, and spread evenly over the plot in shallow standing water.

Postinoculation management

1. After inoculation, raise water level to the uppermost seedling node. Maintain this level for the first few weeks.
2. Once seedlings start to elongate, flood the tank to maintain water level at the uppermost node. This is necessary for 34 months after inoculation.

Observation and sampling

1. Inspect plants regularly for chlorotic discoloration of the leaf base, just below the collar. This discoloration is characteristic of ufra dur-

Rice variety classification.

Plant condition	Nematodes/tiller (av no.)	Infestation (%)	Reaction ^a
No disease symptom	None	Nil	HR
No disease symptom	1-100	1-20	R
Disease symptom visible	1-100	1-20	R
Disease symptom visible	101-300	21-60	I
Disease symptom visible	300+	61-100	S

^aHR = highly resistant. R = resistant, I = intermediate, S = susceptible.

ing vegetative phase and may be visible 3-4 weeks after inoculation. It more often is visible after 6-7 weeks, but 3-4 months is recommended to allow full development of chlorosis and spread of nematodes. At 3-4 months randomly sample at least 5 plants from each line.

Laboratory processing of plant samples

1. Dissect the individual plant to innermost tender leaf, cut into pieces about 5 mm long, place in a bijou bottle (or other small vial), add 2 ml tap water, loosely cover, and leave overnight.
2. Shake the container to thoroughly mix suspension. Examine 1 ml under a stereomicroscope, using a 1-ml Peters mounting slide to count nematodes. A few nematodes

should be examined by compound microscope (100×–400×) to ascertain the proportion of *D. angustus* in the sample.

3. Calculate total number of nematodes per tiller, average number of nematodes per tiller, and percentage of infestation of each variety or breeding line.

Scoring rice varieties

Classify the test varieties into the categories in the table.

Precautions

Some varieties may not show a consistent relation between the average number of nematodes per tiller and the observed percentage of infestation. Such varieties should be left as unclassified and considered for retesting. *h*

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Selection for rice cold tolerance using grain yields versus phenotypic acceptability

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In the rice cold tolerance nursery, selection is based on leaf color, panicle exsertion, growth duration, fertility, and phenotypic acceptability (PA). However, the ultimate measure of performance is grain yield and field performance. An observational yield trial for low temperature areas was started in 1980 at Chuncheon Experiment Station, Korea, to study PA and compare yields. One hundred entries were planted in 1980 and in 1981.

Many entries yielded high (see table) but some yielded low because of high sterility, caused partly by delayed heading.

Several lines of IR crosses yielded high indicating the improvement rice breeders have made on old varieties. In most crosses, Kn-1b-361 was important. IR9202 (IR2053-521-1-1/K116//Kn-1b-361) was promising. IR2053 was early and had good grain quality. K116, from India, and Kn-1b-361, from Indonesia, are cold tolerant.

Cold tolerance at panicle initiation and flowering stage must be improved for Chianan 2, Chianung 242, K-84, and Khonorollo. They are high yielding under moderate temperatures but showed low percentage of fertility in

Results of the 1980-81 observational yield trial for low temperature areas, Chuncheon, Korea.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)	PA
<i>1980</i>		
China 988	6.81	5
IR7167-33-2-3-3-1-3	6.45	3
IR9202-5-2-2	6.60	5
IR9202-6-1-1-2-2	6.51	3
IR9202-10-2-1-1-3	6.85	5
IR9202-10-2-1-5-1	6.30	5
IR15636-8-3	7.30	5
IR15889-32-1	7.89	7
Shoa-Nan-Tsan	6.45	5
SR3044-78-3	7.30	3
SR4079-4-2	6.30	9
Cheoulwon 21 (check)	5.51	5
<i>1981</i>		
SR5204-91-4-1	6.92	3
IR15924-265-3	6.69	6
IR9202-33-4-2-1	6.41	5
IR7167-33-2-3-3-1-3-1	6.40	3
IR20897-B-45	6.28	3
Suweon 235 (check)	3.77	3